

(ALMOST) PERFECT HETERONUCLEAR SYSTEM – NMR RELAXATION THEORY VERSUS EXPERIMENT

Adriane Consuelo Leal Auccaise¹, Elzbieta Masiewicz¹, Radoslaw Cybulski², Bartosz Nowak²,
Danuta Kruk^{1,*}

¹Department of Physics and Biophysics, University of Warmia and Mazury in Olsztyn,
Oczapowskiego 4, 10-719 Olsztyn, Poland

²Faculty of Mathematics and Computer Science, University of Warmia and Mazury in Olsztyn,
Słoneczna 54, 10-710 Olsztyn, Poland

*Corresponding author: danuta.kruk@uwm.edu.pl

Keywords: Nuclear Magnetic Resonance, relaxation theory, spin systems, dynamics,
fluoroaniline

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PLEASE CITE THIS ARTICLE AS DOI: 10.1063/5.0290899

Abstract

^1H and ^{19}F spin-lattice relaxation studies were performed for partially deuterated 3-fluoroaniline-2,4,6- d_3 , ND_2 ($\text{FC}_6\text{HD}_3\text{ND}_2$) in the frequency range from 10 kHz to 20 MHz (referring to ^1H resonance frequency) at 208 K, 218 K, 228 K and 238 K. The molecules contain single ^1H and ^{19}F nuclei in geometrically equivalent positions and therefore this compound was selected as an example of a heteronuclear (^1H , ^{19}F) spin system. The well-known spin relaxation theory developed for a model system including two spins (that can be exemplified by a single molecule of 3-fluoroaniline-2,4,6- d_3 , ND_2) has been adopted (extended) to “real” systems (including many molecules) by taking into account relaxation pathways associated with the intermolecular ^1H - ^1H , ^{19}F - ^{19}F and ^1H - ^{19}F magnetic dipole-dipole interactions. The theoretical framework was applied to interpret the ^1H and ^{19}F spin-lattice relaxation data aiming to assess how accurately the model reproduces the experimental results. The relaxation theory predicts bi-exponential relaxation processes for heteronuclear spin systems; the vi-exponentiality is, however, rarely observed experimentally. The reason of this effect was discussed for 3-fluoroaniline-2,4,6- d_3 , ND_2 treated as an example.

I. Introduction

Nuclear Magnetic Resonance (NMR) relaxation processes arise from a combination of the quantum-mechanical properties of spin systems and the dynamics of the involved molecules and ions. The underlying quantum-mechanical framework of spin relaxation is governed by the spin interactions. Spins (magnetic moments) interact with an external magnetic field (the Zeeman interaction). For spins $\frac{1}{2}$ the Zeeman interaction determines the energy level structure of the spin system (in some cases the energy levels can be affected by scalar interactions). For higher spin quantum numbers, quadrupole interactions can contribute to (sometimes even dominate) the energy level structure. In this work we focus on spins $\frac{1}{2}$ and, consequently, a Zeeman energy level structure. The relaxation processes (transitions between the energy levels) are primarily driven by magnetic dipole-dipole interactions that stochastically fluctuate in time due to molecular motion. To describe the relaxation processes by the second rank perturbation theory (which constitutes the foundation of the Redfield relaxation theory) one has to unambiguously split the total Hamiltonian, describing all relevant spin interactions, into a time independent part (the Zeeman coupling in this case) determining the energy level structure and a time dependent part (the dipole-dipole interactions in this case) causing transitions between the energy levels.¹⁻⁹ The time-dependent (perturbing) Hamiltonian is given as a product of spin tensor operators and time-dependent functions (including Wigner rotation matrices). Consequently, for sufficiently fast dynamics (short correlation times) one can express the spin relaxation rates as linear combinations of spectral density functions (Fourier transforms of the corresponding time correlation functions characterizing the stochastic fluctuation of the perturbing interactions).⁶⁻¹² The combination of the spectral densities is determined by the quantum-mechanical framework of the relaxation processes, why the mathematical forms of the spectral density functions reflect the mechanism of motion.^{2, 3, 8, 13-19}

For a system of two non-equivalent nuclei (nuclei characterized by different gyromagnetic factors) of spin quantum numbers $\frac{1}{2}$, such as ^1H and ^{19}F , the transitions leading to a change in the ^1H magnetization (^1H spin-lattice relaxation) and ^{19}F magnetization (^{19}F spin-lattice relaxation) are intertwined, by cross-relaxation terms. This^{2, 8, 9, 20-24} implies that the spin-lattice relaxation processes of both species involved are, in principle, bi-exponential.^{2, 8, 20-23} The same can be said about a nuclear spin – electron spin system. This theoretical finding established many years ago forms the fundamentals of spin relaxation theory.

Experimentally, one rarely observes bi-exponential relaxation processes for systems that are homogenous from the point of view of the molecular (ionic) dynamics. There are many reasons for this. The first one is that to observe bi-exponentiality, the two relaxation rates should

considerably differ - if the ratio between the relaxation rates is rather of the order of 2 than 10, a single-exponential fit reproduces the time evolution of the magnetisation sufficiently well (especially taking into account that the data include experimental uncertainties). On the other hand, because of experimental limitations (the ranges of relaxation rates accessible for a specific equipment), it is difficult (impossible) to simultaneously probe relaxation processes occurring on timescales differing by orders of magnitude. One should also take into account the ratio between the amplitudes of the two relaxation contributions. The ratio depends on the values of the relaxation and cross-relaxation rates as well as the initial values of the magnetization for both species involved in the relaxation process (the magnetization depends on the abundance, gyromagnetic factors and experimental settings). The amplitudes should be comparable – otherwise, one of the components becomes negligible. Following this line, when one of the species relaxes much faster than the other one (this is the case of the electron spin relaxation in a nuclear spin – electron spin system), the magnetization of the first one reaches its equilibrium very fast and then the relaxation process becomes single exponential. One should also realize that the relaxation expression derived for a model, two spin system (I and S) cannot be directly applied because for “real” systems there are other spin interactions (not only the mutual $I - S$ dipole – dipole coupling) that lead to other relaxation pathways. These interactions can be of intra-molecular and inter-molecular origin and, consequently, fluctuate in time due to different mechanisms of motion. On top of this complex scenario, there is also the subject of dynamical heterogeneity. The presence of molecular fractions of different mobility in the slow exchange limit contribute to the complexity.

As far as the experimental progress is concerned, the possibility of performing relaxation experiments over a broad range of resonance frequencies (exploiting the Fast Field Cycling technique^{25,26}) brings a new dimension to relaxation studies. This kind of experiments is referred to as NMR relaxometry and the covered frequency range encompasses at least three orders of magnitude, from 10 kHz to 10 MHz or higher (referring to ^1H resonance frequency). The intrinsic property of relaxation processes is that the transitions between the energy levels are most efficient when the time scale of the modulations of the spin interactions causing these transitions matches the reciprocal resonance frequency (the gap between the Zeeman energy levels for a spin $1/2$). This implies that at low resonance frequencies one probes slow molecular motion, while with increasing the frequency progressively faster dynamics is detected. Thus, by changing the resonance frequency makes it possible to probe molecular motion on the time scale from milliseconds to nanoseconds in a single experiment. Moreover, as relaxation rates are expressed as linear combinations of spectral density functions, the shape of the frequency

dependence of the relaxation rates reflects the mechanism of the motion (the mathematical forms of the spectral density function are motion specific, as already pointed out).

We have selected partially deuterated 3-fluoroaniline, $\text{FC}_6\text{HD}_3\text{ND}_2$ (containing single ^1H and ^{19}F nuclei in geometrically equivalent positions), as a heteronuclear system to investigate the extent to which theoretical predictions can agree with experimental results when both thorough experimental effort and a suitable theoretical model are employed. We wish to point out that we do not question the correctness of the fundamental relaxation theory. Our aim is to enquire into the real level of agreement taking into account relaxation pathways which are always present (one can hardly perform NMR experiments for a single molecule, just a two-spin system) and the experimental accuracy.

II. Theory

Molecules of partially deuterated 3-fluoroaniline, $\text{FC}_6\text{HD}_3\text{ND}_2$, include a single ^1H nucleus and a single ^{19}F nucleus per molecule. Consequently, the ^1H spin-lattice relaxation rate, $R_{1\text{H}}(\omega_{\text{H}})$ (ω_{H} denotes ^1H resonance frequency in angular frequency units), stems from three relaxation contributions associated with the corresponding dipole-dipole interactions: ^1H - ^1H and ^1H - ^{19}F inter-molecular relaxation contributions ($R_{1\text{H},\text{inter}}^{\text{HH}}$ and $R_{1\text{H},\text{inter}}^{\text{HF}}$, respectively) and ^1H - ^{19}F intra-molecular relaxation contribution ($R_{1\text{H},\text{intra}}^{\text{HF}}$):

$$R_{1\text{H}}(\omega_{\text{H}}) = R_{1\text{H},\text{inter}}^{\text{HH}}(\omega_{\text{H}}) + R_{1\text{H},\text{inter}}^{\text{HF}}(\omega_{\text{H}}) + R_{1\text{H},\text{intra}}^{\text{HF}}(\omega_{\text{H}}) \quad (1)$$

The well-known expressions for spin-lattice relaxation rates for homo-nuclear ($I - I$) and hetero-nuclear ($I - S$) pairs of spins $\frac{1}{2}$ (R_{1I}^{II} and R_{1I}^{IS} , respectively) yield^{2,3,6,8,9,18,19,21,24,27-30}:

$$R_{1I}^{\text{II}}(\omega_I) = C_{\text{DD}}^{\text{II}} [J(\omega_I) + 4J(2\omega_I)] \quad (2)$$

$$R_{1I}^{\text{IS}}(\omega_I) = C_{\text{DD}}^{\text{IS}} [J(\omega_I - \omega_S) + 3J(\omega_I) + 6J(\omega_I + \omega_S)] \quad (3)$$

where ω_I and ω_S denote the resonance frequencies (in angular frequency units) of the I and S spin, respectively, while $C_{\text{DD}}^{\text{II}} = \frac{3}{10} \left(\frac{\mu_0 \gamma_I^2 \hbar}{4\pi r_{\text{II}}^3} \right)^2$ and $C_{\text{DD}}^{\text{IS}} = \frac{1}{10} \left(\frac{\mu_0 \gamma_I \gamma_S \hbar}{4\pi r_{\text{IS}}^3} \right)^2$ denote the corresponding dipolar relaxation constants; r_{II} , r_{IS} are the $I - I$ and $I - S$ inter - spin (inter - nuclei) distances, respectively, γ_I and γ_S denote the I and S spin gyromagnetic factors, respectively, while the other symbols have their well-known meaning. The quantity $J(\omega)$ is referred to as a spectral density function and it is defined as Fourier transform of the corresponding time correlation function characterizing stochastic fluctuations of the dipole-dipole interactions. Intra-molecular

dipole-dipole interactions are modulated by rotational dynamics of the molecules, while the predominant source of modulations of inter-molecular dipole-dipole interactions is relative translation diffusion of the interaction molecules. Consequently, the intra-molecular relaxation term of Eq. (1) can be expressed as:^{3,8,9,17,18,19,31}

$$R_{1H,intra}^{HF}(\omega_H) = C_{DD}^{HF} \left[\frac{\tau_c}{1+(\omega_H-\omega_F)^2\tau_c^2} + \frac{3\tau_c}{1+(\omega_H\tau_c)^2} + \frac{6\tau_c}{1+(\omega_H+\omega_F)^2\tau_c^2} \right] \quad (4)$$

where ω_F denotes ^{19}F resonance frequency in angular frequency units, while τ_c is the rotational correlation time of fluoroaniline molecule. In Eq. (4) the intra-molecular (rotational) spectral density is expressed in a Lorentzian form. The inter-molecular ^1H - ^1H relaxation contribution is given as:^{3,8,9,15,18,31-38}

$$R_{1H,inter}^{HH}(\omega_H) = \frac{108}{5} \left(\frac{\mu_0}{4\pi} \gamma_H^2 \hbar \right)^2 \frac{N}{d^3} \int_0^\infty \frac{u^4}{81+9u^2-2u^4+u^6} \left[\frac{\tau_{trans}}{u^4+(\omega_H\tau_{trans})^2} + \frac{4\tau_{trans}}{u^4+(2\omega_H\tau_{trans})^2} \right] du \quad (5)$$

The parameter τ_{trans} denotes the translational correlation time defined as: $\tau_{trans} = \frac{d^2}{2D_{trans}}$, where D_{trans} is the translation diffusion coefficient, while d is referred to as a distance of the closest approach and can be approximated by the diameter of the molecule. The form of the spectral density used in Eq. (5) stems from the hard sphere force free model that assumes isotropic translation diffusion of molecules treated as hard spheres with spins in their centre. The parameter N is the number of ^1H nuclei per unit volume, however, as for $\text{FC}_6\text{HD}_3\text{ND}_2$ the numbers of ^1H and ^{19}F nuclei per unit volume are identical, we use N for ^1H and ^{19}F ; γ_H and γ_F are ^1H and ^{19}F gyromagnetic ratios, respectively, other symbols have their well-known meaning. Following this line, the $R_{1H,inter}^{HF}(\omega_H)$ relaxation contribution is given as:

$$R_{1H,inter}^{HF}(\omega_H) = \frac{36}{5} \left(\frac{\mu_0}{4\pi} \gamma_H \gamma_F \hbar \right)^2 \frac{N}{d^3} \int_0^\infty \frac{u^4}{81+9u^2-2u^4+u^6} \left[\frac{\tau_{trans}}{u^4+(\omega_H-\omega_F)^2\tau_{trans}^2} + \frac{3\tau_{trans}}{u^4+(\omega_H\tau_{trans})^2} + \frac{6\tau_{trans}}{u^4+(\omega_H+\omega_F)^2\tau_{trans}^2} \right] du \quad (6)$$

In Eq. (5) and Eq. (6) we set $d_{HH} = d_{HF} = d$ (the ^1H - ^1H and ^1H - ^{19}F distances of the closest approach are equal). To simplify the further discussion, the final expression for $R_{1H}(\omega_H)$ takes the form:

$$R_{1H}(\omega_H) = \frac{108}{5} \left(\frac{\mu_0}{4\pi} \gamma_H^2 \hbar \right)^2 \frac{N}{d^3} \int_0^\infty \frac{u^4}{81+9u^2-2u^4+u^6} \left[\frac{\tau_{trans}}{u^4+(\omega_H\tau_{trans})^2} + \frac{4\tau_{trans}}{u^4+(2\omega_H\tau_{trans})^2} \right] du + \frac{36}{5} \left(\frac{\mu_0}{4\pi} \gamma_H \gamma_F \hbar \right)^2 \frac{N}{d^3} \int_0^\infty \frac{u^4}{81+9u^2-2u^4+u^6} \left[\frac{\tau_{trans}}{u^4+(\omega_H-\omega_F)^2\tau_{trans}^2} + \frac{3\tau_{trans}}{u^4+(\omega_H\tau_{trans})^2} + \frac{6\tau_{trans}}{u^4+(\omega_H+\omega_F)^2\tau_{trans}^2} \right] du + C_{DD}^{HF} \left[\frac{\tau_c}{1+(\omega_H-\omega_F)^2\tau_c^2} + \frac{3\tau_c}{1+(\omega_H\tau_c)^2} + \frac{6\tau_c}{1+(\omega_H+\omega_F)^2\tau_c^2} \right] \quad (7)$$

Analogously, one obtains for the ^{19}F spin-lattice relaxation rate:

$$R_{1F}(\omega_F) = R_{1F,inter}^{FF}(\omega_F) + R_{1F,inter}^{FH}(\omega_F) + R_{1F,intra}^{FH}(\omega_F) \quad (8)$$

that implies:

$$R_{1F}(\omega_F) = \frac{108}{5} \left(\frac{\mu_0}{4\pi} \gamma_F^2 \hbar \right)^2 \frac{N}{d^3} \int_0^\infty \frac{u^4}{81+9u^2-2u^4+u^6} \left[\frac{\tau_{trans}}{u^4+(\omega_F\tau_{trans})^2} + \frac{4\tau_{trans}}{u^4+(2\omega_F\tau_{trans})^2} \right] du + \frac{36}{5} \left(\frac{\mu_0}{4\pi} \gamma_H \gamma_F \hbar \right)^2 \frac{N}{d^3} \int_0^\infty \frac{u^4}{81+9u^2-2u^4+u^6} \left[\frac{\tau_{trans}}{u^4+(\omega_H-\omega_F)^2\tau_{trans}^2} + \frac{3\tau_{trans}}{u^4+(\omega_F\tau_{trans})^2} + \frac{6\tau_{trans}}{u^4+(\omega_H+\omega_F)^2\tau_{trans}^2} \right] du + C_{DD}^{FH} \left[\frac{\tau_c}{1+(\omega_H-\omega_F)^2\tau_c^2} + \frac{3\tau_c}{1+(\omega_F\tau_c)^2} + \frac{6\tau_c}{1+(\omega_H+\omega_F)^2\tau_c^2} \right] \quad (9)$$

with $C_{DD}^{FH} = C_{DD}^{HF}$. Taking into account that $\frac{\omega_F}{\omega_H} = \frac{\gamma_F}{\gamma_H} = 0.94$, the relaxation rates $R_{1H}(\omega_H)$ and $R_{1F}(\omega_F)$ should be similar.

Mathematical properties of the spectral density describing the translation diffusion lead to a linear dependence of the relaxation rate on squared root of the resonance frequency in the low frequency range (where $\omega\tau_{trans} \ll 1$). For a system consisting of one kind of nuclei of spin $\frac{1}{2}$ (^1H , ^{19}F) the relationship between the slope of the linear dependence, B , is related to the translation diffusion coefficient, D_{trans} :^{9,31,33,35-39}

$$R_1(\omega) \cong R_1(0) - B\sqrt{\omega} = R_1(0) - N\pi \left(\frac{1+4\sqrt{2}}{30} \right) \left(\frac{\mu_0}{4\pi} \gamma^2 \hbar \right)^2 D_{trans}^{-3/2} \sqrt{\omega} \quad (13)$$

where ω and γ are the resonance frequency and the gyromagnetic factor of the nucleus. On the basis of Eq. (13) one can formulate expressions linking the low frequency slopes of $R_{1H}(\omega_H)$ and $R_{1F}(\omega_F)$ (B_H and B_F , respectively) with the translation diffusion coefficient:^{37, 38}

$$B_H = - \left[N_H \pi \left(\frac{1+4\sqrt{2}}{30} \right) \left(\frac{\mu_0}{4\pi} \gamma_H^2 \hbar \right)^2 + N_F \pi \left(\frac{1+2\sqrt{2}}{30} \right) \left(\frac{\mu_0}{4\pi} \gamma_H \gamma_F \hbar \right)^2 \right] D_{trans}^{-3/2} \quad (14)$$

$$B_F = - \left[N_F \pi \left(\frac{1+4\sqrt{2}}{30} \right) \left(\frac{\mu_0}{4\pi} \gamma_F^2 \hbar \right)^2 + N_H \pi \left(\frac{1+2\sqrt{2}}{30} \right) \left(\frac{\mu_0}{4\pi} \gamma_H \gamma_F \hbar \right)^2 \right] D_{trans}^{-3/2} \quad (15)$$

In Eq. (14) and Eq. (15) it has been assumed that $\omega_H \cong \omega_F$.

III. Materials and methods

3-fluoroaniline-2,4,6-d₃,ND₂ was purchased from Merck® company. ¹H and ¹⁹F spin-lattice relaxation experiments were performed in the frequency range from 10 kHz to 20 MHz (referring to ¹H resonance frequency) using a SpinMaster Fast Field Cycling (FFC) NMR relaxometer (Stelar s.r.l., Mede, Italy). The spin-lattice relaxation measurements were performed at 208 K, 218 K, 228 K and 238 K (with 1 K accuracy using a built-in temperature controller). Below 10 MHz pre-polarization at 0.47 T was applied. The switching time of the magnet was set to 3 ms. The magnetization versus time was recorded for logarithmically distributed time points; 32 acquisitions were performed.

The melting temperature for fluoroaniline is about 240K. This implies that the liquid was in supercooled state.

IV. Results and analysis

Fig. 1(a),(b) shows ¹H and ¹⁹F spin-lattice relaxation data for 3-fluoroaniline-2,4,6-d₃,ND₂ obtained at 208 K, 218 K, 228 K and 238 K. The ¹H relaxation data shown in Fig. 1(a) have been added to Fig. 1(b) for comparison.

FIG. 1. (a) ¹H and (b) ¹⁹F spin-lattice relaxation rates for 3-fluoroaniline-2,4,6-d₃,ND₂, solid lines in (b) ¹H spin-lattice relaxation rates data of (a) shown for comparison.

The relaxation processes have turned out to be single exponential for all temperatures in the whole frequency range as shown in Fig. 2(a)-(h) for selected cases.

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FIG. 2. ¹H and ¹⁹F magnetization versus time obtained by FFC NMR for 3-fluoroaniline-2,4,6-d₃,ND₂ at selected resonance frequencies in the temperatures range of 208 K – 238 K. Top and right axis corresponds to frequencies 490 (464) kHz and 10 (9.4) kHz, while bottom and left axis for 20 (18.8) MHz and 11.1 (10.5) MHz. Solid lines - single exponential fits.

Before proceeding with a detailed analysis of the ¹H and ¹⁹F spin-lattice relaxation data shown in Fig. 1, we shall exploit the relationships of Eq. (14) and Eq. (15) to determine the translation diffusion coefficients, D_{trans} , with the expectation that both data sets (¹H and ¹⁹F) will give similar results. Fig. 3 shows the relaxation rates plotted versus square root of the corresponding resonance frequencies. The expected linear dependencies are clearly present. Table I includes the values of the translation diffusion coefficient, D_{trans} , obtained from Eq. (14) applied to the ¹H spin-lattice relaxation data and Eq. (15) to the ¹⁹F data. The number of ¹H or ¹⁹F nuclei per unit volume have been obtained from the relationship: $N = \frac{N_A \rho}{M}$, where N_A is the Avogadro's number, $\rho = 1.156 \text{ g/cm}^3$ and $M = 116.15 \text{ g/mol}$ denote density and molecular mass of 3-fluoroaniline-2,4,6-d₃,ND₂; one obtains $N = 5.99 \times 10^{27} / \text{m}^3$. As expected, the diffusion coefficients are in a very good agreement.

FIG. 3. ^1H (squares) and ^{19}F (circles) spin-lattice relaxation rates for 3-fluoroaniline-2,4,6- d_3 , ND_2 versus $\sqrt{\omega_H}$ and $\sqrt{\omega_F}$ at (a) 208 K, 218 K and (b) 228 K, 238 K, respectively. Solid lines – linear dependences.

Table I. Translation diffusion coefficients, D_{trans} obtained from the low frequency slopes of $R_1(\omega_H)$ ($R_1(\omega_F)$) versus $\sqrt{\omega_H}$ ($\sqrt{\omega_F}$) (Eq. (14) and (15)) and from the analysis of $^1\text{H}/^{19}\text{F}$ spin-lattice relaxation data for 3-fluoroaniline-2,4,6- d_3 , ND_2 by using Eq. (7) and Eq. (9), respectively; $N_H=N_F=N=5.99 \times 10^{27}/\text{m}^3$; $d=(2.30 \pm 0.02) \text{ \AA}$ (^1H) and $d=(2.56 \pm 0.03) \text{ \AA}$ (^{19}F).

Temp. [K]	D_{trans} [m^2/s] (^1H); slope	D_{trans} [m^2/s] (^{19}F); slope	D_{trans} [m^2/s] (^1H)	D_{trans} [m^2/s] (^{19}F)
208	$(1.57 \pm 0.04) \times 10^{-13}$	$(1.50 \pm 0.03) \times 10^{-13}$	$(1.52 \pm 0.02) \times 10^{-13}$	$(1.40 \pm 0.02) \times 10^{-13}$
218	$(8.25 \pm 0.15) \times 10^{-13}$	$(7.79 \pm 0.09) \times 10^{-13}$	$(8.20 \pm 0.03) \times 10^{-13}$	$(7.65 \pm 0.03) \times 10^{-13}$
228	$(4.07 \pm 0.10) \times 10^{-12}$	$(4.08 \pm 0.10) \times 10^{-12}$	$(4.44 \pm 0.02) \times 10^{-12}$	$(4.21 \pm 0.02) \times 10^{-12}$
238	$(9.72 \pm 0.25) \times 10^{-12}$	$(9.86 \pm 0.36) \times 10^{-12}$	$(1.12 \pm 0.04) \times 10^{-11}$	$(1.04 \pm 0.03) \times 10^{-11}$

In the next step we have reproduced the ^1H and ^{19}F spin-lattice relaxation data (shown in Fig. 1) in terms of Eq. (7) and Eq. (9), respectively. Fast rotational motion of 3-fluoroaniline molecules combined with the relatively small dipolar relaxation constant, C_{DD}^{HF} , makes the intramolecular relaxation contributions, $R_{1H,intra}^{HF}$ and $R_{1F,intra}^{FH}$ (to the ^1H and ^{19}F relaxation, respectively) negligible. This implies that both data sets have been reproduced in terms of two adjustable parameters, D_{trans} and d (the last one kept temperature independent). The outcome

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^1H spin-lattice relaxation rate, R_1 [s^{-1}]

of the analysis for ^1H spin-lattice relaxation is presented in Fig. 4(a). Fig. 4(b)-(d) shows the decomposition of the overall ^1H spin-lattice relaxation rates into the $R_{1\text{H},inter}^{HH}$ and $R_{1\text{H},inter}^{HF}$ terms. Fig. 4 (b),(c) show, in addition the decomposition of the $R_{1\text{H},inter}^{HF}$ relaxation contribution into the part including only the spectral density taken at the difference between the resonance frequencies, $(\omega_H - \omega_F)$, and the part including the sum of the spectral densities at ω_H and $(\omega_H + \omega_F)$. The obtained values of the translation diffusion coefficient, D_{trans} , are in a very good agreement with those obtained from the linear dependence of $R_{1\text{H}}$ on $\sqrt{\omega_H}$ (Table I). For the distance of the closest approach, d , the value of 2.30 Å was obtained.

FIG. 4. (a) ^1H spin-lattice relaxation data for 3-fluoroaniline-2,4,6- d_3 , ND_2 reproduced in terms of Eq. (7) – solid lines; the ^1H spin-lattice relaxation data and the corresponding fits for: (b) 208 K, (c) 218 K, (d) 228 K and 238 K, decomposed into the relaxation contributions, $R_{1\text{H},inter}^{HH}$ – dashed lines and $R_{1\text{H},inter}^{HF}$ – dashed- dotted lines; (b) and (c) includes the decomposition of $R_{1\text{H},inter}^{HF}$ into the part including the spectral density taken at $(\omega_H - \omega_F)$ – black dashed-dotted

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line, and the part including the sum of the spectral densities at ω_H and $(\omega_H + \omega_F)$ – black dashed line.

As far as the ^{19}F spin-lattice relaxation data are concerned, the corresponding fits are presented in Fig. 5(a), while the decomposition into the individual relaxation contributions, $R_{1F,inter}^{FF}$ and $R_{1F,inter}^{FH}$, is shown in Fig. 5(b)-(d). In analogy to the ^1H relaxation, Fig. 5(b),(c) shows, in addition the decomposition of the relaxation contribution $R_{1F,inter}^{FH}$ into the part including only the spectral density taken at the difference between the resonance frequencies, $(\omega_H - \omega_F)$, and the part including the sum of the spectral densities at ω_F and $(\omega_H + \omega_F)$.

FIG. 5. (a) ^{19}F spin-lattice relaxation data for 3-fluoroaniline-2,4,6- d_3 , ND_2 reproduced in terms of Eq. (9) – solid lines; the ^{19}F spin-lattice relaxation data and the corresponding fits for: (b) 208 K, (c) 218 K, (d) 228 K and 238 K, decomposed into the relaxation contributions, $R_{1F,inter}^{FF}$ – dashed lines and $R_{1F,inter}^{FH}$ – dashed-dotted lines; (b) and (c) includes the decomposition of $R_{1F,inter}^{FH}$ into the part including the spectral density taken at $(\omega_H - \omega_F)$ – black dashed-dotted line, and the part including the sum of the spectral densities at ω_F and $(\omega_H + \omega_F)$ – black dashed line; (a) includes theoretical curves obtained for $d=2.30$ Å (as obtained from the analysis of the ^1H spin-lattice relaxation data) for a comparison – grey dashed lines.

The translation diffusion coefficients obtained from this analysis are very close to those obtained from the low frequency linear dependencies (Table I). However, to get the agreement with the experimental ^{19}F spin-lattice relaxation rates, a somewhat longer distance of the closest approach is needed: $d=2.56$ Å. Fig. 5(a) shows theoretical curves calculated for the parameters obtained from the analysis of the ^1H spin-lattice relaxation data, for a comparison.

Finishing this section, we would like to point out that $\rho=1.156\text{g/cm}^3$ corresponds to non-deuterated fluoroaniline at room temperature. One can expect that for 3-fluoroaniline-2,4,6- d_3 , ND_2 the density is of about 4% higher (scaling with the molecular mass). Furthermore, taking into account the values of volumetric expansion coefficients for small aromatic molecules,⁴⁰ one can estimate the increase of the density of 3-fluoroaniline-2,4,6- d_3 , ND_2 at 208K compared to the non-deuterated counterpart at room temperature as about 10%. This difference is of minor importance - the increasing of the N number by 10% can be compensated by increasing d by 3% and D_{trans} by 5%.

V. Discussion

The structure of 3-fluoroaniline-2,4,6- d_3 , ND_2 and the similar ^1H and ^{19}F gyromagnetic ratios bring one to the immediate conclusion that the ^1H and ^{19}F spin-lattice relaxation rates should be similar. Using Eq. (7) and Eq. (9) and knowing that the intra-molecular relaxation contribution is negligible, one can estimate the low frequency limit for the $\frac{R_{1F}}{R_{1H}}$ as being of about 0.86, while the experimental ratios are of about 0.83; the agreement is very good. The consistency of the analysis is reflected by the very good agreement between the translation diffusion coefficients obtained from the ^1H and ^{19}F relaxation data (one should notice that Eq. (14) and Eq. (15) do not include the distance of the closest approach, d). In this context, it is

worth to mention the consistency of the diffusion coefficients obtained for ionic liquids on the basis of ^1H and ^{19}F relaxation data, achieved by including ^1H - ^{19}F relaxation contributions.⁴¹ The diffusion coefficients match also the values estimated for non-deuterated fluoroaniline obtained by means of static field gradient, analyzing the echo decay.⁴² As far as the distances of the closest approach obtained from the analysis of the ^1H and ^{19}F relaxation data are concerned, the deviations can be attributed to the experimental (in)accuracy which includes not only the uncertainties of the exponential fits (Fig. 2), but also instrumental limitations (such as the signal to noise ratio). Such effects are seen, for instance, at high frequencies for slow relaxation processes – Fig. 4(d) and Fig. 5(d) (some jumps in the relaxation rates around 10 MHz). Another possible reason can be related to the arrangement for the molecules (formation of dimers^{43,44}) which might render the ^1H - ^1H and ^{19}F - ^{19}F distances not equal. This effect might manifests itself by the differences in the distances of the closest approach obtained from the analysis of the ^1H and ^{19}F spin-lattice relaxation data.

As already pointed out, both ^1H and ^{19}F relaxation processes have turned out to be single-exponential. To enquire into this subject, one needs to keep in mind the expression for the cross-relaxation rate^{9,22,23}

$$R_1^{cross} = C_{DD}^{IS} [6J(\omega_I + \omega_S) - J(\omega_I - \omega_S)] \quad (16)$$

The relaxation rates characterizing the bi-exponential relaxation, predicted by the theory, are then given as:^{9,22,23}

$$R_1^{\pm} = \frac{1}{2}(R_{1H} + R_{1F}) \pm \frac{1}{2}\sqrt{(R_{1H} - R_{1F})^2 + 4(R_1^{cross})^2} \cong R_1 \pm R_1^{cross} \quad (17)$$

where it has been set: $R_{1H} \cong R_{1F} \cong R_1$. Taking into account Eq. (7) (and Eq. (9)) one can estimate the ratio between these two relaxation rates in the extreme narrowing condition (for $\omega\tau_c \ll 1$) as: $\frac{R_1^+}{R_1^-} \cong \frac{3}{2}$. This explains why the time evolution of the ^1H and ^{19}F magnetizations can be sufficiently well described as single-exponential (the theoretically predicted relaxation rates are similar). In the high frequency range, for relatively slow dynamics (208K), the relaxation rates R_1 (and R_1^{cross}) are dominated by the spectral density at $(\omega_H - \omega_F)$, as shown in Fig. 4(b) and Fig. 5(b). Then the relaxation process tends to be single exponential with the relaxation rate getting closer to $2R_1$. Nevertheless, one should note that this is a limiting case and for faster dynamics all relaxation terms contribute to the relaxation rates (Fig. 4(c) and Fig. 5(c)), eventually approaching the estimations of the low frequency range for progressively faster motion. One can add to this picture also the possibility of a chemical shift anisotropy contribution to the ^{19}F spin-lattice relaxation at higher frequencies, although one can expect that the contribution is not significant (if not negligible) because of the low frequency range covered

in the experiment, combined with fast rotational dynamics. It has been demonstrated in detail, for fluorine containing ionic liquids, that the relaxation contribution associated with chemical shift anisotropy becomes visible above about 100MHz.⁴⁵ The interplay between the outlined factors has implied that although the relaxation processes are theoretically not purely single-exponential, the limited experimental accuracy makes the single-exponential approach sufficient and does not justify bi-exponential fits.

Performing this work, we aimed at testing the theoretical description developed for a two-spin model system (being a basics of the spin relaxation theory) against experimental data for a system resembling the model one. As already pointed out, the presence of several relaxation pathways is not avoidable for real systems. Thus, we presented an extension of the model to make it appropriate for analyzing relaxation processes in real, heteronuclear systems and tested its performance. As NMR relaxometry is widely used to get insight into molecular and ionic motion, we are of the opinion that the thorough reminder of the quantum-mechanical framework of spin relaxation will increase the awareness of the complexity of the relaxation phenomena.

VI. Conclusions

This work presents the outcome of the comparison of the relaxation theory with ^1H and ^{19}F spin-lattice relaxation data, collected over a broad frequency range, for a system resembling as close as possible a model, heteronuclear spin system. The extension of the theory (including inter-molecular relaxation pathways) made it possible to perform the comparison with the experiment. The essence of the comparison lies in the small differences between the ^1H and ^{19}F relaxation rates expected as a result of the equivalent geometrical positions of ^1H and ^{19}F in the molecule and the similar gyromagnetic factors of both nuclei. The consistency of the data analysis requires that the similar ^1H and ^{19}F relaxation rates are reproduced in terms of the same parameters (the translation diffusion coefficient and inter-spin distances). At the same time one should be aware of the uncertainties of the experimental data. Moreover, although the relaxation processes can be reproduced using single exponential functions, they can be, to some extent, affected by this simplification. In our opinion, the agreement between the theory and the experiment and the level of the consistency of the analysis proves the credibility of the model and accuracy of the experimental data.

Acknowledgement

This research has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under grant agreement No 899683 (project "HIRES-MULTIDYN").

Data Availability

The data that support the findings of this study are available from the corresponding author upon request.

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PLEASE CITE THIS ARTICLE AS DOI: 10.1063/5.0290899

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